

Development of a Secure Web-Based Logbook System for the Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme

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Abstract

The Student Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is a vital component of undergraduate education in Nigeria, aimed at equipping students with hands-on industrial experience. However, the traditional paper-based SIWES logbook poses several challenges, including susceptibility to loss or damage and limited effectiveness in supervision and feedback. To address these limitations, this study developed a secure web-based SIWES logbook system, incorporating the Bcrypt (Blowfish) algorithm and JSON Web Tokens (JWT) to safeguard user data and prevent unauthorized access. The system enables students to digitally record their daily industrial activities while allowing both academic and industry supervisors to monitor progress and provide timely feedback. Key features include online accessibility, an intuitive user interface, and strong data security mechanisms. An online survey was conducted to assess the system's usability and effectiveness, with responses collected from 20 SIWES participants. The findings revealed a high level of user satisfaction: 65% of respondents found the system very easy to navigate, 65% rated the instructions as very clear, and 56.3% found it easy to log daily or weekly activities. Regarding security and trust, 60% felt their data was secure. Additionally, 90% of respondents preferred the web-based system over the traditional paper logbook, and 100% agreed that the platform was easy for new users to adopt. Overall, the system demonstrated strong potential in improving the SIWES experience, with user suggestions guiding future enhancements.

Keywords: SIWES, Web-Based Logbook, Data Security, Bcrypt Algorithm, Usability

INTRODUCTION

The Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES), established in 1973 by the Industrial Training Fund (ITF), aims to equip Nigerian undergraduates with practical industrial skills before graduation. Students must obtain SIWES registration forms and a paper logbook to record their daily activities during the industrial placement. They make daily entries and submit the log weekly for verification, comments, and supervisors' signatures. Despite its importance, the paper-based logbook faces challenges such as high printing costs, administrative tasks, monitoring difficulties, and delays in assessing student progress. Issues may go unresolved until the end, and students risk data loss due to inadequate organizational resources or lost/damaged logbooks. (Adetiba *et al.*, 2012). These issues are further compounded by the lack of continuous oversight and feedback throughout the training period.

Various studies have proposed solutions like digital logbooks to improve SIWES management, including web and mobile platforms for real-time activity logging, supervision, and documentation, enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and oversight (Adetiba *et al.*, 2012; Olojakpoke & Ojo, 2020; Omonijo *et al.*, 2020; Samed *et al.*, 2022; Olasehinde *et al.*, 2022;

Nugraha *et al.*, 2023; Adekunle *et al.*, 2024). Despite this, most systems prioritise usability but lack strong security, leaving logbook data vulnerable to threats like unauthorised access and breaches. In a digital age with growing cyber threats, security is vital to maintaining system trustworthiness.

This study develops a secure web-based SIWES logbook system, featuring advanced security mechanisms, including bcrypt encryption. The system provides a centralized, secure, and interactive platform for activity logging, communication, and oversight. Key functionalities include multimedia uploads, secure authentication, and role-based access control. The Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA) served as the case study for evaluating the system, which aims to improve efficiency, transparency, and security in Nigerian tertiary institutions.

METHODOLOGY

The secure SIWES web-based logbook system was developed using the Waterfall software development life cycle model, which involves phases of requirement gathering, system design, implementation, testing, and deployment. Its architecture has four layers: Presentation, Application, Data, and Security, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Secure Web-based Logbook System Architecture

The web-based logbook system supports four user roles: student, school supervisor, industry supervisor, and system administrator, who is the Industrial Training Coordinator. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) ensures that each user accesses only relevant features and data on both the frontend and backend. Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) restricts system functionalities to authorized users (Ferraiolo *et al.*, 1999), as expressed in Equation (1):

$$A(u, r, f) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } r \in R_u \text{ and } f \in F_r \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $A(u, r, f)$ is the access permission for the user u with role r to functionality f , R_u is the set of roles assigned to the user, and F_r is the set of functions accessible to the role r .

Presentation Layer

The presentation layer, built with ReactJS, is the client-side visual and interactive interface. Figure 2 illustrates user actions after login, categorised by role. Students register and manage logbook entries. Industry supervisors review logbooks and provide feedback. School supervisors offer feedback and evaluate students. System administrators handle user accounts, system monitoring, backups, and access control.

Figure 2. Secure Web-based Logbook System Users’ Roles Flowchart

Application Layer

The application layer, built with Nodejs, manages core system functions like request processing, responses, validations, and data handling. It defines system components' structure and behaviour through a class diagram, showing objects, attributes, methods, and relationships. Figure 3 shows the class diagram of the secure web-based logbook system.

Figure 3. Secure Web-based Logbook System Class Diagram

Data Layer

The data layer manages data storage and retrieval with a MySQL relational database, organizing data into tables of entities with defined relationships. Each table has rows and columns representing properties and connections. Figure 4 shows the database model, its entities, attributes, and relationships.

Figure 4. Entity Relationship diagram

Security Layer

The security layer was built using Bcrypt and JSON Web Tokens (JWT) as shown in Equations (2) and (3), which provide a secure and scalable foundation. Bcrypt employs salting combined with the Blowfish algorithm to hash passwords securely, generating unique hashes even for identical passwords and making them resistant to brute-force attacks through iterative hashing controlled by a cost factor. JWT facilitates stateless user authentication and authorization by encoding user information in tokens issued upon login, which are then included in client requests for server-side verification without maintaining session data. Together, these technologies enhance the system's overall security by protecting user credentials and efficiently managing secure access. Figure 5 shows the steps involved in secure user registration and login using Bcrypt.

Figure 5. Bcrypt process for login and sign-up

Passwords are hashed with Bcrypt (Provos & Mazieres, 1999), a salted Blowfish-based algorithm (Fig. V), defined in Equation (2).

$$H = \text{Bcrypt}(P, S) \quad (2)$$

where H is the hashed password, P is the plaintext password, and S is a randomly generated salt. This method mitigates brute-force and rainbow table attacks, ensuring secure storage of credentials.

Upon login, a JSON Web Token (JWT) is generated to authenticate the user without relying on server-side sessions (Dalimunthe *et al.*, 2023), JWT enables secure, server-independent session validation as described in Equation (3):

$$T = \text{JWT}(H, C, exp) \quad (3)$$

where H is the hashed password, C contains user claims and role information, and exp denotes the token expiration time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed system centralizes and secures logbook management for students, supervisors, and administrators, with detailed results on its interfaces. The web-based system provides login portals for each role, which have links for registration and login pages. The Submit Details Page (Figure 6) lets new users request registration without logging in. After administrator approval, an email verification link is sent to confirm identity. Once verified, the user is prompted to create a password, hashed with Bcrypt and Blowfish securely.

Figure 6. Submit Details Page

After successful login after registration, a JSON Web Token (JWT) is generated to manage user sessions and ensure secure authentication throughout their interaction with the system. The Login Page depicted in Figure 7 allows students to log in using their matriculation number and password, the industry supervisors use their email and password, the school supervisors log in with their Staff ID and password, and the administrators access the system using their email and password.

Figure 7. Login Page

Upon logging in, users view role-specific dashboards (Figures 8-11). Students submit reports and upload evidence of their SIWES progress. School supervisors monitor performance via log entries, photos, and information using matriculation numbers. Industry supervisors review and comment on activities every week for evaluation. Administrators control system tools, user accounts, activity monitoring, and data management for efficient oversight.

Figure 8. Student Dashboard Page

Figure 9. School Supervisor Page

Figure 10. Industry Supervisor Page

Figure 11. Admin Dashboard Page

The results of this study are consistent with existing literature (Warschauer and Matuchniak; Frank *et al.*, 2021), demonstrating that digital platforms enhance usability, transparency, and communication in academic supervision. Participants' positive perceptions of the system's security features reinforce findings from prior research that emphasize the importance of strong authentication and cryptographic protection in educational technologies (Bonneau *et al.*, 2012). Furthermore, the preference for a web-based solution aligns with broader trends toward digital transformation in education, which aim to reduce administrative burdens and improve data accessibility (Al-Fraihat *et al.*, 2020).

System Evaluation and User Feedback Analysis

After deploying the web-based logbook system, a user evaluation was conducted using Google Forms to gather structured feedback. The system was evaluated using Google Forms, with responses collected from 20 SIWES participants, comprising 17 500-level students, 2 school supervisors, and 1 industrial supervisor at the Federal University of Technology, Akure. The survey included a Likert scale and open-ended questions covering system effectiveness, user satisfaction, ease of use, security, and preference and adoption. These were analysed directly within Google Forms based on participant inputs, and the results provide valuable insights for refining the system to meet user needs better.

The evaluation results shown in Figure 12 – 17 indicate that 65% of the users find the logbook system very satisfactory, 65% of the users found the logbook system easy to navigate, 100% find the logbook system easy to adopt and learn, with clear instructions and an intuitive design, and 56.3% find the logbook system easy to log their daily/weekly activities. Regarding security, 40% of users find the logbook system very secure, and 60% find it secure. Notably, 90% preferred the web-based logbook over the traditional paper-based version.

Figure 12. User Experience

Figure 13. Ease of Use and Navigation

Do you believe that the app is easy for new users to adopt and learn?

Figure 14. User Interactions

How easy was it to log your daily/weekly activities in the logbook app?

Figure 15. Ease of Logging Activities

How do you feel about the security of your data within the logbook app?

Figure 16. Data Security

If you have used a paper-based logbook before, which do you prefer: the paper-based or web-based logbook?

Figure 17. Web-based Preference

CONCLUSION

This project successfully developed and deployed a secure web-based logbook system by replacing traditional paper-based logbook methods. Focusing on usability, data security, and role-based access, the system integrates encryption, session management, and user-specific dashboards. A user evaluation was carried out with 20 participants from the Federal University of Technology, Akure. Results showed that 65% of users were very satisfied, 65% found the system easy to navigate, and 100% reported it was easy to learn and adopt. Additionally, 56.3% reported ease in logging activities, 60% rated the system secure, and 90% preferred it over the paper-based alternative. These outcomes confirm the system's effectiveness in improving usability, security, and efficiency. This research has limitations, including the absence of an ITF Officer module and the exclusion of the final submission and approval process by the SIWES/IT Unit coordinator. Future work will address these gaps by adding the ITF Officer module, integrating the final submission process, and conducting security tests. Additional improvements may include the integration of Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning and automated backups to enhance system robustness, usability, and scalability.

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